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A Preliminary Study on Amphibian-Feeding Behavior of Hematophagous Diptera (Psychodidae, Culicidae, and Corethrellidae) in Taiwan Based on Citizen Science Data

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Abstract. In recent years, concerns about pathogen transmission among amphibians by hematophagous insects have been increasing. However, records of dipteran hematophagy on amphibians remain scarce in Taiwan, leaving a significant knowledge gap in understanding this host–parasite interaction. In this study, we conducted a citizen science project to collect photographic records of Diptera feeding on amphibian blood and analyzed their associated families and seasonal peaks of hematophagous activity. Members of three dipteran families (Psychodidae, Culicidae, and Corethrellidae) were observed feeding on amphibians representing four anuran families (Bufonidae, Dicroglossidae, Ranidae and Rhacophoridae). Notably, this study provides the first record of sand flies (Psychodidae: Phlebotominae) feeding on amphibians in Asia, as well as the first direct observational evidence of this worldwide. Based on these occurrence data, we further constructed species distribution models (SDMs) for each of these amphibian-feeding dipteran families, providing a preliminary insight into the diversity and spatial patterns of this ecological interaction.

Key words: Diptera, Corethrellidae, Culicidae, Psychodidae, Phlebotominae, hematophagy, amphibian

Introduction

Hematophagy is a widely shared behavior among insect lineages and has evolved independently multiple times (Deepak & Shruti, 2024). Among all taxa exhibiting this behavior, the dipteran family Culicidae has been particularly well studied, since they often serve as vectors of lethal pathogens such as dengue virus (Gloria et al., 2014) and malaria (Godfray, 2013) which cause millions of human deaths each year (Fang et al., 2011). However, the hosts of hematophagous Diptera are not limited to humans or mammals, as amphibians represent one of the common blood sources for these insects. In recent years, growing concern over the global decline of amphibians (Luedtke et al., 2023) has led researchers to focus on interspecific interactions involving dipteran insects that feed on anuran blood. These insects, including the genera *Corethrella* and *Culex*, have been reported to carry lethal pathogens such as *Batrachochytrium dendrobatidis* (Bd) and frog trypanosomes and may act as potential disease-transmitting vectors (Ramos & Urdaneta-Morales, 1977; Reinhold et al., 2023; Toledo et al., 2021).

In Taiwan, studies on amphibian-feeding hematophagous insects are still limited. Bang et al. (2025) conducted a study in central Taiwan using frog-calling traps to collect two dipteran families (Culicidae and Corethrellidae) and four species captured attracted by anuran mating calls. In the same year, the frog-biting midge *Corethrella nippon* was recorded feeding on the critically endangered *Nidirana shyhhuangi* (You et al., 2026), raising concerns about potential pathogen transmission involving this rare species (Toledo et al., 2021). In this study, we utilized citizen science image data to broaden the detection of amphibian-feeding insects that may not rely on frog calls as cues for host searching.

Materials and methods

Data collection

We reviewed a total of 10,080 images of anurans in Taiwan on iNaturalist to find photos of blood-feeding interactions between anurans and hematophagous Diptera. We also created a Google Form to collect photographs documenting observations of dipterans feeding on amphibian blood. The form was promoted through online citizen science and nature photography communities on Facebook, including the “Taiwan Amphibian Conservation Volunteers” (Chinese: 台灣兩棲保育志工) and the “Abnormal Herp

Photos” (Chinese: 不正常兩棲爬行動物貼圖區). For each observation, we recorded the amphibian host at the species level, along with the time period, geographic location, and family-level identity of the hematophagous Diptera. In this study, dipterans were categorized into three families according to their feeding posture. Phlebotominae, a subfamily of Psychodidae, were readily distinguishable from Corethrellidae and Culicidae by their distinctive behavior of holding their wings open while feeding (Figure 1A). Corethrellidae (Figure 1B) and its closely related taxon, Culicidae (Borkent, 2008; Wood, 1989; Figure 1C), exhibit a broadly similar feeding posture, as they close their wings during feeding; however, they were characterized by shorter mouthparts and a feeding stance in which all six legs typically rest on the host (Downes, 1958). In addition, the body length of Corethrellidae species is typically around 1 mm, which is substantially smaller than that of Culicidae.

Figure 1. Feeding postures of (A) Psychodidae, (B) Corethrellidae, and (C) Culicidae. Photographs by Ming Shu Chan, Tsan-Ran Tseng, and Yi-Chen Chang.

Statistical analysis

We applied the Watson–Williams test to analyze the seasonality of hematophagous behavior among different Dipteran families that feed on amphibians and employed the MaxEnt model with 19 bioclimatic variables from WorldClim to predict the potential geographic distribution of each amphibian-feeding Dipteran family. All model settings were evaluated using the *ENEvaluate* package in R and implemented in MaxEnt version 3.4.4. (Phillips et al., 2017; Team, 2020).

Results

We collected a total of 31 photographic records of Diptera feeding on amphibians, including 1 record from iNaturalist and 30 records from the Google form (Figure 2). Phlebotominae accounted for 48.3% ($n = 15$) of the total records, followed by Culicidae, which accounted for 32.3% ($n = 10$). Although highly specific to anuran blood, the Corethrellidae represented the smallest proportion, comprising 12.9% (6) of the total records (Figure 3). Regarding the amphibian hosts, a total of four out of six native frog families (Bufonidae, Dicroglossidae, Ranidae and Rhacophoridae) were recorded in this study (Table 1; Figure 4), with Hylidae and Microhylidae absent.

Results of the Watson–Williams test indicated that the timing of feeding behavior did not differ significantly among the three Dipteran families, and all photographic records were taken between May and November (Figure 5). The predicted potential distributions of the three frog-biting Dipteran families showed distinct spatial patterns. The probability of occurrence for frog-biting Phlebotominae was higher in low-elevation areas, particularly in northeastern Taiwan. In contrast, Corethrellidae were predicted to occur more frequently in high-elevation mountain regions. For frog-biting Culicidae, only extremely high-elevation areas were predicted to be unsuitable (Figure 6).

Figure 2. Distribution in Taiwan of Dipteran families feeding on amphibians.

Figure 3. The proportion of hematophagous Dipteran families recorded feeding on amphibian blood.

Figure 4. The proportion of anuran families that served as hosts for hematophagous Diptera.

Figure 5. The monthly distribution of photographic records of the three Dipteran families feeding on amphibians.

Figure 6. Predicted potential distributions of the three frog-biting Dipteran families generated using the MaxEnt model.

Discussion

Anurans are vertebrates with highly diverse calling behaviors, which are often exploited by hematophagous insects that eavesdrop on these acoustic signals as cues for host location (Bernal & de Silva, 2015). In a study by Bang et al. (2025), four Culicidae species and one Corethrellidae species were collected in Taiwan using frog-calling traps. However, Phlebotominae, which were not captured in the frog-calling traps, are the most frequently observed anuran blood-feeding dipterans in our citizen science investigation. This suggests that Phlebotominae may rely on alternative cues for host-seeking. Moreover, Phlebotominae were observed feeding on species that do not typically vocalize, such as *Bufo bankorensis*, indicating a potential knowledge gap when assessing frog-biting insects solely through call-based trapping methods. This study provides the first record of Phlebotominae feeding on amphibian blood in Asia, as well as the first direct observational evidence worldwide of this feeding behavior. Previously, such interactions had only been detected through molecular data from South America (Costa et al., 2021), underscoring the importance of further investigation into whether these insects carry pathogens and pose potential risks of disease transmission among amphibians.

All recorded observations occurred between May and November, which may be related to the fact that summer represents the peak breeding season for amphibians in Taiwan, as mating calls have been considered one of the key cues for host seeking by both Corethrellidae and Culicidae (Bang et al., 2025; Bernal & de Silva, 2015). However, given the small sample size, this pattern may also reflect a detection bias associated with seasonal herping activity, as naturalists and photographers tend to conduct more field trips during summer. If Phlebotominae indeed do not rely on frog advertisement calls as host-seeking cues, they may still be capable of locating amphibian hosts outside of the breeding season.

Overall, we highlight the potential of citizen science as a valuable tool in parasitological research, particularly for host species that are cryptic or otherwise difficult to observe directly. Similar methodological approaches have recently been applied to investigate predatory interactions in rove beetles by Hu et al. (2025), underscoring the broader applicability of citizen science-based data collection. In this study, most photographic records were obtained incidentally while participants were filming frogs, which likely contributed to a relatively low detection rate, as individuals sometimes moved the frogs during photography. In addition, the image quality of the insects was often insufficient to allow identification beyond the family level. A more systematic survey targeting hematophagous insects feeding on amphibians would provide clearer insights into their phenology and enable higher-resolution taxonomic identification.

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References

- Bang, W. J., You, J. Y., Bae, Y., Chuang, M. F. & Shin, S. 2025. Preliminary Study on Host Use and Phylogenetic Analysis of *Corethrella nippon* in Taiwan. *Ecology and Evolution* 15 (11): e72405.
- Bernal, X. E. & de Silva, P. 2015. Cues used in host-seeking behavior by frog-biting midges (*Corethrella* spp. Coquillet). *Journal of Vector Ecology* 40 (1): 122–128.
- Borkent, A. 2008. The frog-biting midges of the world (Corethrellidae: Diptera). *Zootaxa* 1804 (1): 1–456.
- Costa, J., Marchi, G., Santos, C., Andrade, M., Chaves Junior, S., Silva, M., Melo, M., & Andrade, A. d. 2021. First molecular evidence of frogs as a food source for sand flies (Diptera: Phlebotominae) in Brazilian caves. *Parasitology Research* 120 (5): 1571–1582.
- Deepak, R. & Shruti, S. 2024. Evolution of Hematophagy in Insects: A new Perspective. *Bulletin of Pure & Applied Sciences-Zoology* 43A (1): 74–77.
- Downes, J. A. 1958. The feeding habits of biting flies and their significance in classification. *Annual Review of Entomology* 3 (1): 249–266.
- Fang, W., Vega-Rodríguez, J., Ghosh, A. K., Jacobs-Lorena, M., Kang, A. & St. Leger, R. J. 2011. Development of transgenic fungi that kill human malaria parasites in mosquitoes. *Science* 331 (6020): 1074–1077.
- Gloria-Soria, A., Brown, J. E., Kramer, V., Hardstone Yoshimizu, M. & Powell, J. R. 2014. Origin of the dengue fever mosquito, *Aedes aegypti*, in California. *PLoS neglected tropical diseases* 8 (7): e3029.
- Godfray, H. C. J. 2013. Mosquito ecology and control of malaria. *Journal of Animal Ecology* 82 (1): 15–25.
- Hu, F.-S., Hsiao, Y. & Solodovnikov, A. 2025. A global citizen science effort via iNaturalist reveals food webs of large predatory rove beetles. *Food Webs* 43: e00399.
- Luedtke, J. A., Chanson, J., Neam, K., Hobin, L., Maciel, A. O., Catenazzi, A., Borzée, A., Hamidy, A., Aowphol, A. & Jean, A. 2023. Ongoing declines for the world's amphibians in the face of emerging threats. *Nature* 622 (7982): 308–314.
- Phillips, S. J., Anderson, R. P., Dudík, M., Schapire, R. E. & Blair, M. E. 2017. Opening the black box: An open-source release of Maxent. *Ecography* 40 (7): 887–893.
- Ramos, B. & Urdaneta-Morales, S. 1977. Hematophagous insects as vectors for frog trypanosomes. *Revista de Biología Tropical*, 25 (2): 209–217.
- Reinhold, J.M.; Halbert, E.; Roark, M.; Smith, S.N.; Stroh, K.M.; Siler, C.D.; McLeod, D.S.; Lahondère, C. 2023. The role of *Culex* territans mosquitoes in the transmission of *Batrachochytrium dendrobatidis* to amphibian hosts. *Parasites & Vectors* 16 (1): 424.
- Team, R. C. 2020. R: A language and environment for statistical computing, R Foundation for Statistical. *Computing*.
- Toledo, L. F., Ruggeri, J., Leite Ferraz de Campos, L., Martins, M., Neckel-Oliveira, S. & Breviglieri, C. P. B. 2021. Midges not only sucks, but may carry lethal pathogens to wild amphibians. *Biotropica* 53 (3): 722–725.
- You, J.-Y., Wang, Y. T. & Chuang, M.-F. 2025. A rare record of a midge biting *Nidirana shyhuangi* Lin et al., 2025 in Taiwan. *Herpetology Notes* 19: 15–16.
- Wood, D. 1989. Phylogeny and classification of the Neenatocera. *Manual of nearctic Diptera* 3: 1333–1370.

從公民科學觀察揭示臺灣吸血性雙翅目（蛾蚋科，蚊科，蛙蠓科）吸食兩生類行為之初探

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摘要：近年來，關於吸血性昆蟲在兩生類間傳播病原體的疑慮日益增加。然而，在臺灣有關雙翅目吸食兩生類血液的紀錄仍相當稀少，使我們對此宿主－吸血昆蟲間互動的了解存在顯著的知識缺口。本研究透過公民科學計畫蒐集吸血性雙翅目吸食兩生類血液的影像紀錄，並分析其所屬科別以及吸血行為的高峰季節。結果顯示共有三科雙翅目昆蟲（蛾蚋科、蚊科、蛙蠓科）吸食了四科無尾目兩生類的血液（蟾蜍科、叉舌蛙科、赤蛙科、樹蛙科）。本文報導亞洲第一筆蛾蚋科之白蛉亞科吸食兩生類血液的行為紀錄，同時也是全球首筆蛾蚋科吸食兩生類的影像紀錄。本文亦以此資料集建立這些雙翅目科別之物種分布模型 (SDMs)，初步揭示此交互作用的多樣性與發生情形。

關鍵詞：雙翅目、蛙蠓科、蚊科、蛾蚋科、白蛉亞科、吸血、兩生類